

ECONOMIC DIVERSIFICATION AND THE OIL SECTOR IN NIGERIA

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Key words:

*Economic
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Dutch Disease,
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time-series
analysis*

Abstract: *This study examined the impact of key economic sectors on diversification efforts in Nigeria from 1986 to 2023, focusing on the oil, manufacturing, services, and agricultural sectors. Using time-series data from the Central Bank of Nigeria and employing the Autoregressive Distributed Lag (ARDL) approach, the research assessed the long- and short-run relationships between sectoral contributions and economic diversification, proxied by real GDP. The findings revealed that while the manufacturing and services sectors exhibited positive but statistically insignificant contributions to diversification, the oil and agricultural sectors showed negative yet insignificant effects. The results indicated no significant individual impact from any of the sectors on economic diversification during the study period, underscoring the persistent challenges in transitioning away from oil dependence and the need for more integrated and effective diversification policies.*

1.0 INTRODUCTION

1.1 Background to the Study

Since the discovery of commercial oil quantities in the late 1950s, Nigeria's economy has become increasingly dependent on petroleum exports, which currently account for over 90% of export earnings and approximately 60% of government revenues (World Bank, 2024). The Nigerian oil sector remains the

backbone of the country's economy, despite decades of calls for diversification. This heavy reliance on oil has created a paradox where abundant natural resources have not translated into sustained economic growth and development for the majority of Nigerians. The petroleum sector has dominated the Nigerian economy for decades, contributing substantially to government revenues and

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foreign exchange earnings. However, this mono-economic structure has exposed the country to external shocks, particularly volatile oil prices, and has constrained the development of other productive sectors (Nigerian Export Promotion Council, 2024).

Despite its oil wealth, Nigeria faces significant developmental challenges, including high unemployment (33.3% as of 2023, NBS), widespread poverty (over 40% of the population living below the poverty line), and infrastructural deficits. The dominance of the oil sector has also led to the neglect of other critical sectors such as agriculture, manufacturing, and solid minerals, which were once the backbone of the economy before the oil era. This phenomenon, often referred to as the "Dutch Disease," has stifled economic diversification and sustainable development (The Economist, 1977; World Bank, 2024; Udeh, Onuoha & Nwokorobia, 2021).

According to African Development Bank (2024), Nigeria's heavy dependence on oil revenues exposes the economy to significant volatility from global oil price fluctuations. This dependency has led to recurring fiscal crises during periods of low oil prices, highlighting the unsustainability of the current economic model. Oil wealth has not translated into adequate infrastructure development or improvement in human development indicators. Nigeria continues to rank poorly on

various development indices despite its oil wealth. The oil sector, being capital-intensive, provides limited direct employment opportunities for the country's growing population, which exceeds 220 million people.

Recent economic indicators highlight the urgent need for diversification. Before the coronavirus (COVID-19) pandemic, Nigeria's oil sector generally accounted for about nine percent of the country's gross domestic product (GDP), while the agricultural sector has shown resilience, with Nigeria's agriculture sector significantly contributing to the country's GDP in Q3 2023, reaching 28.65%. The services sector has also emerged as a significant contributor, with the performance of the GDP in the fourth quarter of 2023 was driven mainly by the services sector (African Development Bank, 2024; Statista, 2024).

Successive governments have recognized the need for economic diversification and have introduced various policies and initiatives, such as the Agricultural Transformation Agenda (ATA), the Economic Recovery and Growth Plan (ERGP), and the National Development Plan (2021–2025), aimed at reducing dependence on oil by promoting sectors like agriculture, solid minerals, ICT, and renewable energy. However, progress has been slow due to structural challenges, including corruption, inadequate infrastructure, insecurity, and inconsistent policy implementation. Given

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Nigeria's growing population (over 220 million according to World Bank, 2024) and the urgent need for job creation and sustainable development, economic diversification remains a critical imperative (World Bank, 2024; African Development Bank).

1.2 Statement of the Problem

Nigeria's economy has historically been heavily reliant on the oil sector, which contributes a significant proportion of government revenue and export earnings. However, this dependence has rendered the economy vulnerable to external shocks, particularly fluctuations in global oil prices. Despite several policy pronouncements on economic diversification, the contribution of non-oil sectors such as agriculture, manufacturing and services remains inadequate to offset the risks associated with oil dependence (Adewuyi & Arawomo, 2020). The oil sector, although a major revenue earner, contributes relatively little to employment and value-added activities compared to agriculture and services. Yet, Real Gross Domestic Product (RGDP) growth trends in Nigeria still tend to mirror the performance of the oil sector, indicating limited success in achieving meaningful economic diversification (CBN, 2021). This structural imbalance has led to macroeconomic instability, high unemployment rates, and persistent poverty (Olayungbo & Quadri, 2019). Nigeria's economic performance remains suboptimal,

characterized by persistent poverty, unemployment, and macroeconomic instability. The fundamental problem lies in the country's failure to effectively leverage oil revenues to diversify its economic base and achieve sustainable growth. This has resulted in a paradoxical situation where Africa's largest oil producer struggles with economic development challenges.

Despite various initiatives such as the Economic Recovery and Growth Plan (ERGP) and the Nigeria Vision 20:2020, the empirical evidence on how sectoral contributions affect economic performance remains inconclusive or under-explored. In light of this, it becomes imperative to empirically examine the relationship between the oil sector and economic diversification efforts in Nigeria. This study seeks to assess how the contributions of the oil, agriculture, manufacturing, and services sectors to GDP influence overall economic performance, as measured by RGDP for a 34-year period (1990-2023). Understanding this dynamic is essential for informing policy decisions aimed at fostering a more resilient and inclusive economy.

1.3 Objectives of the Study

This study seeks to assess the impact of economic diversification away from the oil sector on Nigeria's economy. However, the specific objectives are as follows:

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1. Examine the impact of the oil sector contribution to economic diversification in Nigeria.
2. Evaluate the effect of the manufacturing sector contribution to economic diversification in Nigeria.
3. Ascertain the effect of the services sector contribution to economic diversification in Nigeria.
4. Analyse the impact of the agricultural sector contribution to economic diversification in Nigeria.

1.4 Research Questions

The following research questions are posed to guide the direction of findings of this study.

1. What is the impact of the oil sector contribution to economic diversification in Nigeria?
2. What is the effect of the manufacturing sector contribution to economic diversification in Nigeria?
3. What is the effect of the services sector contribution to economic diversification in Nigeria?
4. What is the impact of the agricultural sector contribution to economic diversification in Nigeria?

1.5 Research Hypotheses

The following research hypotheses are in their null forms

1. HO_1 : Oil sector contribution has no significant impact to economic diversification in Nigeria.
2. HO_2 : Manufacturing sector contribution has no significant effect to economic diversification in Nigeria.
3. HO_3 : Services sector contribution has no significant effect to economic diversification in Nigeria.
4. HO_4 : Agricultural sector contribution has no significant impact to economic diversification in Nigeria.

1.6 Significance of the Study

Studying economic diversification and the oil sector in Nigeria is significant for several reasons. Nigeria is one of Africa's largest economy and the oil sector has played a significant role in its growth. However, the country's heavy reliance on oil revenue has also made it vulnerable to fluctuations in global oil prices and has hindered the development of other sectors of the economy.

Economic diversification is crucial for Nigeria's long-term economic growth and stability. By diversifying the economy, Nigeria can reduce its dependence on oil revenue and develop other sectors such as agriculture, manufacturing, and services. This can lead to job creation, increased productivity, and higher economic growth.

The oil sector is also important for Nigeria's economic development. Nigeria is Africa's

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largest oil producer and the oil sector accounts for a significant percentage of the country's GDP and government revenue. However, the oil sector has also been associated with environmental degradation, conflict, and corruption.

Therefore, studying economic diversification and the oil sector in Nigeria is important for understanding the country's economic development and for identifying strategies for promoting sustainable growth and reducing dependence on oil revenue.

1.7 Scope of the Study

The scope of this study is within the period of 1986 – 2023 (38 years). This study is particularly concerned with the need for economic diversification over growing concerns of global uncertainties with the crude oil market. The study considers economic diversification index (proxied by RGDP) as the dependent variable; while oil sector contribution to GDP, agricultural sector contribution to GDP, manufacturing sector contribution to GDP and the services sector contribution to GDP are the explanatory variables of interest of interest that would guide the study.

2.0 LITERATURE REVIEW

2.1 Conceptual Review

2.1.1 Economic Diversification

According to the International Monetary Fund (IMF, 2014), economic diversification refers to

the process of shifting an economy away from a single income source (often raw materials like oil, minerals, or agriculture) toward multiple sectors to create a more balanced and resilient economic structure. This involves developing new industries, expanding services, and fostering innovation to reduce dependence on a narrow range of exports or revenue streams.

Why is Economic Diversification Important?

The United Nations Conference on Trade and Development (UNCTAD, 2016), noted that economies reliant on a single sector (e.g., oil, mining) are highly exposed to price fluctuations, demand shocks, and depletion risks. Diversification spreads risk (UNCTAD, 2016), argued. African Development Bank (AfDB, 2019), contend that a diversified economy encourages innovation, job creation, and long-term stability by developing multiple competitive industries and further argued that by investing in technology, manufacturing, and services, countries can integrate into global value chains. In the views of Cherif & Hasanov (2019); Organization of Economic Cooperation and Development (OECD, 2018) and World Bank (2021), new industries create jobs in different sectors, reducing reliance on a single employer or industry as a varied economy is more appealing to foreign and domestic investors looking for stability and opportunities.

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Economic diversification in Nigeria refers to the country's strategic effort to reduce its heavy dependence on oil revenues by developing and strengthening other sectors of the economy. This has become increasingly critical as Nigeria faces the challenges of volatile oil prices and the need for sustainable economic growth. According to Riti, Gubak & Dankumo (2016), Nigeria's major development challenge is not the 'oil curse', but of achieving economic diversification beyond its dependence on oil revenues, with politics playing an important role in policy choices that have created this challenge. The concept involves expanding the economic base beyond petroleum to create a more balanced and resilient economy. According to the Carnegie Endowment for International Peace (2022), the Nigerian government has implemented specific frameworks and actionable plan across three sectors: agro-allied, solid minerals and oil and gas-related industries, where Nigeria's comparative and competitive advantage are apparent.

2.1.2 The Nigerian Oil Sector

The oil sector in Nigeria from has been a critical pillar of the economy, structured into three main segments: upstream, midstream, and downstream. The upstream segment involves exploration, development, and production of crude oil and natural gas. It is capital intensive and dominated by the

Nigerian National Petroleum Corporation (NNPC) and International Oil Companies (IOCs), which contribute about 94% of total production. Oil blocks and mining licenses are awarded to both indigenous companies and IOCs, with the Department of Petroleum Resources (DPR) overseeing licensing. Production Sharing Contracts (PSC) and Service Contracts (SC) govern operations, with PSCs allowing foreign participation in deep and ultra-deep water exploration. The midstream sector handles transportation, storage, and processing of crude oil and gas, ensuring secure and efficient movement from production sites to refineries and markets. Pipelines and storage facilities are key infrastructure components, while the downstream sector constitutes the processing of crude oil into petroleum products for domestic consumption by local refineries, although refining capacity has historically been limited (Morohunfola, 2024; Nigeria National Petroleum Corporation, 1999; CBN, 2002).

Nigeria's oil sector contribution to GDP has shown a general decline in its share of the economy, despite remaining a critical revenue source. Historically, before the COVID-19 pandemic, the oil sector contributed about 9% to Nigeria's GDP. However, this share dropped significantly during and after the pandemic, reaching 5.9% in late 2020 and further declining to around 5.48% by the third quarter of 2023 (Statista, 2023; National Bureau of

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Statistics, 2024). According to KPMG (2024) and Thisday Newspaper (2024), the sector's real growth has been volatile, with negative growth rates during the pandemic years (e.g., -8.89% in 2020, -8.30% in 2021, and -19.22% in 2022), but showing signs of recovery with a -2.22% contraction in 2023 and positive quarterly growth in late 2023. Oil production fluctuations, from over 2 million barrels per day in early 2020 to about 1.35 million barrels per day by October 2023, have directly influenced the sector's GDP contribution (Statista, 2023; National Bureau of Statistics, 2024). Despite the declining GDP share, the oil sector remains vital, generating over 80% of government revenues and approximately 95% of foreign exchange earnings, underscoring Nigeria's economic dependence on oil (Njoku, Ndifon & Apaingolo, 2025). Overall, Nigeria's oil sector contribution to GDP has decreased from around 9% to about 5.5%, reflecting production challenges, global price shocks, and economic diversification efforts, though it remains a cornerstone of government revenue and export earnings.

2.1.3 The Manufacturing Sector in Nigeria

The manufacturing sector encompasses a wide range of industries, including cement production, beverages, oil refining, food, tobacco, textile, rubber processing, footwear, paper, chemical, and pharmaceutical

production. The manufacturing sector in Nigeria contributes significantly to the country's GDP, although its share has experienced fluctuations and declines in recent years due to various economic challenges. In 2023, the manufacturing sector's value added as a percentage of GDP was reported at 15.36% (World Bank, 2025). Textile and cement sectors were notable contributors within the manufacturing sector in 2023, with shares of 1.5% and 0.8% respectively. For the third quarter of 2023, the manufacturing sector contributed 16.18% to nominal GDP. However, its contribution to real GDP in the same quarter was 8.43%, a slight decrease from 8.59% in Q3 2022. The sector's contribution to GDP saw a marginal decline from 16.18% in Q3 2023 to 16.04% in Q4 2023, reflecting ongoing struggles (Tunji, 2024; NBS, 2023; CBN, 2024). According to Onwuamaeze (2025), challenges such as high energy prices, exorbitant exchange rates, soaring interest rates, persistent inflation, and unstable fuel supply have impacted the sector. Reforms like fuel subsidy removal and exchange rate unification have also led to increased production costs and reduced consumer purchasing power.

2.1.4 The Services Sector in Nigeria

Nigeria's service sector has grown to become the largest contributor to the country's GDP, reflecting a shift from agriculture and industry

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towards services such as telecommunications, financial services, technology, and entertainment according to CBN (2024). The sector includes telecommunications, financial services, information technology, tourism, entertainment, trade, transport, and other business services. It is a mixed economy focus area, with growing urbanization driving demand for services. The key components are banking, insurance, telecommunications, and IT services, which have expanded rapidly in recent decades. In 1986, the service sector contributed a smaller share compared to agriculture and industry, but it steadily grew over time. By 2023, the service sector accounted for approximately 42.77% of Nigeria's GDP, making it the largest sector by share (Statista, 2024). The sector's growth has been a major driver of overall GDP growth, with services contributing over half (52.7%) of GDP growth in Q3 2023 alone. The sector's expansion reflects Nigeria's transition towards a more diversified economy, reducing overreliance on oil and agriculture. Despite fluctuations in other sectors, services have maintained relatively stable growth, supported by urbanization and technological adoption (NBS, 2024). Nigeria's service sector has evolved from a minor contributor in the 1980s to the dominant economic sector by 2023, contributing about 43% of GDP. This shift is driven by growth in telecommunications,

finance, and technology, underpinning Nigeria's mixed and emerging market economy (NBS, 2024; USAID, 2017).

2.1.4 The Agricultural Sector in Nigeria

The Nigerian agricultural sector is composed of four main sub-sectors: Crop production, Livestock, Forestry and Fishing. Crop production is the dominant sub-sector, accounting for the largest share of agricultural output and engaging about 70% of farming households. Livestock rearing is most prevalent in the northwest, while fishing is more common in the southern regions. Forestry, though smaller in scale, remains an important component for rural livelihoods and environmental sustainability (Food and Agricultural Organization, 2020; Adams, Obonyilo & Kolawale, 2024). Key crops include maize, cassava, yam, guinea corn (sorghum), groundnut, rice, millet, and beans. Nigeria is the world's largest producer of cassava, yam, taro, cowpea, and sorghum, and among the top producers of okra, peanut, sweet potato, ginger, millet, and palm oil. Cash crops such as cocoa, rubber, palm oil, groundnut, and sesame are grown for export and domestic industry (Akinboyo, 2008; Food and Agricultural Organization, 2020).

Nigeria has approximately 70.8 million hectares of agricultural land, with 34 million hectares arable, 6.5 million for permanent

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crops, and 30.3 million as meadows and pastures. However, only about 42% of the cultivable area is actively farmed, and most holdings are small-scale and scattered, relying on traditional tools and methods (World Bank, 2020; FAO, 2020). Agriculture remains Nigeria's largest employer, accounting for up to 35% of total employment as of 2020, and providing livelihoods for the majority of the rural population (Jlukom, 2022; Adeite, 2022). Historically, agriculture was the backbone of Nigeria's exports, with cash crops like cocoa, groundnut, and palm oil dominating before oil became the primary export commodity in the 1970s. Over time, the sector's export role diminished, and Nigeria became increasingly reliant on food imports, especially wheat and other staples, due to population growth and underinvestment in local production (Akinboyo, 2008; Food and Agricultural Organization, 2020). In the late 1980s and throughout the 1990s, agriculture's share of GDP remained significant, averaging around 30% (Chukwu, 2023). In 2001, agriculture contributed 32% to GDP. By the third quarter of 2019, the sector contributed 29.25% to real GDP. In Q2 2023, agriculture generated about 21% of Nigeria's GDP, maintaining its role as a major economic sector despite a gradual decline in relative contribution as the economy diversified and the oil sector expanded (FAO, 2020).

Nigeria's agricultural sector remained a cornerstone of the economy in terms of GDP contribution, employment, and food security. The sector is dominated by crop production, with significant outputs in cassava, yam, and other staples, alongside important but smaller contributions from livestock, forestry, and fishing. Despite growth in output, the sector faces challenges such as underinvestment, reliance on imports, and limited modernization, all of which have affected its overall contribution to national development.

2.1.5 Economic Growth from the Perspective of Diversification

Economic growth refers to the increase in the production of goods and services in an economy over time, leading to higher income and improved living standards. Economic diversification is the process of shifting an economy from reliance on a single income source to multiple sources across various sectors and markets, thereby fostering more stable and sustainable growth (United Nations, 2005). In Nigeria, economic growth is closely linked to diversification because the economy has historically depended heavily on oil exports, which account for over 90% of export revenue and about 80% of government revenue. This mono-product dependence exposes Nigeria to volatility from oil price fluctuations and limits broad-based development (Anyaeie & Areji, 2015).

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Diversification involves expanding other sectors such as agriculture, manufacturing, services, and solid minerals to reduce this dependency and create multiple income and employment sources (Anyaehe & Areji, 2015; Usman, 2022).

2.2 Theoretical Literature

2.2.1 Dutch Disease Theory

Dutch Disease refers to the paradox where the discovery or exploitation of natural resources (particularly oil) leads to a decline in other productive sectors of the economy, such as agriculture and manufacturing. This concept was first used to describe the Netherlands' economic issues following the discovery of natural gas in the 1960s (Corden & Neary, 1982). The influx of foreign exchange from resource exports appreciates the real exchange rate, making non-resource exports less competitive, and results in a reallocation of labor and capital toward the booming resource sector at the expense of others. The term was coined in 1977 by The Economist to describe the decline of the manufacturing sector in the Netherlands after the discovery of the large Groningen natural gas field in 1959 (The Economist, 1977).

Nigeria presents a classic case of Dutch Disease. The country's heavy dependence on crude oil, which accounts for over 90% of export earnings and more than 60% of government revenue (CBN, 2021), has led to

the neglect of agriculture and manufacturing - sectors that were previously the backbone of the economy.

Exchange Rate Effects: The oil boom, especially during the 1970s and 2000s, led to a real appreciation of the naira. This made Nigerian non-oil exports less competitive in global markets and discouraged foreign investment in non-oil sectors (Ogun, 2010).

Deindustrialization: Manufacturing's share of GDP has remained low, fluctuating between 7% and 10% over the last two decades (World Bank, 2022). Investment has been skewed toward oil infrastructure, while industrial capacity utilization remains low.

Neglect of Agriculture: Before oil discovery, agriculture contributed more than 60% to GDP and employed over 70% of the labor force. However, by the 2000s, its contribution dropped significantly as public investment shifted towards oil, weakening rural economies and food security (Suberu, Ajala & Akande, 2015).

Government Spending Pattern: Oil revenues have led to pro-cyclical fiscal policies, with increased spending during oil booms, often on non-productive ventures or recurrent expenditure, without corresponding investment in economic diversification (Iyoha & Oriakhi, 2002).

2.2.2 The Dual Sector Model

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The Dual Sector Model, developed by W. Arthur Lewis (1954), is one of the foundational theories in development economics that explains the process of structural transformation in developing countries. The model divides the economy into two main sectors: the traditional (subsistence) sector, predominantly characterized by agriculture and low productivity, and the modern (capitalist) sector, which comprises industry and services with higher productivity and returns on labour. According to Lewis, economic development occurs as labour moves from the traditional sector, where there is surplus labour and marginal productivity is close to zero, to the modern sector, where productivity is significantly higher. The modern sector pays wages slightly above the traditional sector to attract labour. Over time, as capital accumulates through reinvested profits in the modern sector, employment expands, productivity rises, and the economy undergoes structural transformation (Lewis, 1954).

Key Assumptions of the Dual Sector Model

1. Existence of surplus labor in the traditional sector.
2. Wage differential exists to motivate migration to the modern sector.
3. Modern sector profits are reinvested to fuel capital accumulation.

4. Full employment in the modern sector is achievable through labour transfer.

The relevance of the Dual Sector Model to Nigeria's economic development lies in its explanation of the country's underutilized labor force, particularly in agriculture and informal sectors, and the stagnation of industrial growth. Despite having a large agricultural base, Nigeria's industrial and manufacturing sectors have remained underdeveloped and unable to absorb surplus labor effectively (Ajakaiye & Jerome, 2014). Empirical studies show that a significant portion of Nigeria's labor force remains engaged in low-productivity activities, while the industrial sector contributes less than 10% to the nation's GDP (World Bank, 2022). This deviates from the expected Lewisian transition, in which the modern sector should progressively expand to dominate output and employment. Olayemi (2012) argues that the failure of Nigeria's modern sector to attract surplus labour is due to poor infrastructure, inconsistent industrial policies, and a mismatch between education outputs and labour market demands. Additionally, rather than reinvesting surpluses from resource revenues (e.g., oil) into labour-absorbing sectors like manufacturing and agro-processing, Nigeria has exhibited a consumption-driven growth pattern that undermines capital accumulation and productivity growth (Iyoha & Oriakhi, 2002).

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While the model provides a useful theoretical lens, its assumptions do not fully align with Nigeria's reality. For instance, the expected surplus labour in rural areas often lacks the skills required for industrial jobs. Furthermore, capital accumulation in Nigeria is often weakened by fiscal mismanagement, corruption, and the capital-intensive nature of oil production (UNIDO, 2020). Despite these limitations, the Dual Sector Model remains a relevant theoretical foundation for understanding the challenges of economic diversification and labour transition in Nigeria.

2.3 Empirical Review

Njoku, Ndifon & Apaingolo (2025), examined the effect of petroleum industry on the Nigerian economy. The time scope of the study covered thirty-four year period which ranged from 1990 to 2023. Ordinary Least Squares (OLS) regression technique was adopted as the technique of data analysis. The findings of the study revealed that there is a positive and significant relationship between petroleum product revenue and Gross Domestic Product in Nigeria, there is a positive and significant relationship between petroleum profit tax and Gross Domestic Product in Nigeria while there is a negative and significant relationship between refined oil import and Gross Domestic Product in Nigeria. Adams, Obonyilo & Kolawale (2024), focused on the contribution of agricultural output from crop production,

livestock, fishing and forestry on Nigeria's GDP contact basic prices. This study utilized panel data estimation, which clearly accounts for variation and examines the parameter's dynamic behavior. The research results show that crop output has a considerable positive effect on GDP, whereas additional agricultural goods such as farm animals, forest products, and fishery have a minor beneficial effect on GDP with correlations. Okulegu (2023), examined the relationship between economic diversification and unemployment in Nigeria for the time span of 1981-2020. Unit Root test, Cointegration test, Vector Error Correction Model (VECM) and Granger Causality test were employed in the analysis. The result revealed that growth rate of both agricultural sector (GRAS) and oil sector (GROS) is positive and statistically significant to unemployment rate in Nigeria; while the of growth rate of manufacturing sector (GRMS) though negatively related to unemployment but statistically insignificant. Utuk, Akpan, Eduno & Udo (2023), used time series data from 2000 to 2022 to assess the impact of agriculture value added on the relationship between agricultural exports and economic growth in Nigeria. The study used the Augmented Dicky-Fuller unit root, Auto-regressive Distributed lag (ARDL) structure and Dynamic Ordinary Least Squares (DOLS) technique for analysis. The study's findings revealed that agriculture

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input exports (LNAGXP) had a positive influence on real GDP, whereas agricultural value added has a negative impact on GDP. Afrogha & Afrogha (2022), investigated if diversification of the economy had any effect on the Nigerian economy from 1986 to 2016. Secondary data were analyzed using the Ordinary Least Square (OLS) method. From the study's results, diversification as measured by agricultural contribution to GDP and mining contribution to GDP, was found to have a significant impact on GDP, whereas manufacturing contribution to GDP was found to have a negative relationship with GDP and a negligible impact on economic growth in Nigeria during the period under review. Edeh, Ogbodo & Onyekwelu (2020), studied the influence of government agriculture spending on the farming output in Nigeria from 1981 to 2018 was assessed using time series data from the Central Bank of Nigeria's Statistical Bulletin and Annual Report. The ARDL model technique study demonstrates that capital expenditure is positively associated to agricultural output, which is also statistically significant at 5% in the present year ($P(t) = 0.0080$)

Using time-series data from 1981 to 2013, Kamil, Sevin and Festus (2017) empirically analysed the impact of Nigerian agribusiness on economic development. In the long run, the results show a balance between real gross

domestic product, agricultural production and oil rents. The results of the vector error correction model show that the rate of adjustment of variables to the long-term equilibrium path is slow, despite the positive impact of agricultural production on economic development. It was proposed that the government and policy makers move towards diversification and increase budget allocations to the agricultural sector.

2.4 Literature/Research Gap

While numerous studies have examined Nigeria's oil dependency and diversification efforts separately, there remains a significant gap in empirically analyzing the simultaneous effects of oil sector performance alongside agricultural and services sector contributions on overall economic growth. Most existing research either focuses solely on oil sector impacts or examines diversification efforts in isolation, without providing a comprehensive quantitative analysis of sectoral interdependencies. The current economic context makes this research particularly relevant. Economic growth is projected to increase to 3.2% in 2024 and 3.4% in 2025, due to improved security, yet challenges persist as the poverty level still remains high, with multidimensional poverty at 63% and income poverty at 40%.

3.0 METHODOLOGY

3.1 Research Design

**Ikwumezie Aham, *Ogu Callistus, Akamike Okechukwu Joseph, Agba Pascal
Ugochukwu and Nwoko Onyeka Bede**

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This study utilized the ex-post factor research design as it deals with events that have taken place and secondary data were available for collection. Diversification index was the explained variable adopted as proxy for diversification index, while the oil sector contribution, manufacturing sector contribution, service sector contribution and agricultural sector contribution were adopted as the explanatory variables.

The theoretical framework of this study anchors on the Dutch Disease theory. The theory explains how a resource boom, such as the discovery of oil, can harm other sectors of the economy through real exchange rate appreciation, making non-resource exports like agriculture and manufacturing less competitive (Corden & Neary, 1982). In Nigeria, oil dominance has led to the decline of agriculture and manufacturing, increased unemployment, and weak economic diversification (CBN, 2023; World Bank, 2020). This highlights the need for policies that reduce oil dependence and support broader economic growth.

3.2 Sources of Data

The data for this study was sourced from the publications of Central Bank of Nigeria Statistical Bulletin, 2024 edition.

3.3 Model Specification

The model for this study is built to establish the functional and causal relationship between oil sector and economic diversification in Nigeria

from 1986 to 2023. In line with the objectives of this study, the model takes the multiple regression structural form below:

$$DIV = f(\text{oil, manufacturing, services, agriculture}) \dots\dots\dots (1)$$

Equation (1) is transformed into a functional model to have:

$$DIV = f(OIL, MFG, SVC, AGR) \dots\dots\dots (2)$$

The functional model of equation (2) is modified into econometric form such that:

$$DIV_t = \beta_0 + \beta_1 OIL_t + \beta_2 MFG_t + \beta_3 SVC_t + \beta_4 AGR_t + \mu_t \dots\dots\dots (3)$$

Further, the natural logarithm of all the variables was taken to curtail the effects of spurious regression. Thus,

$$LN DIV_t = \beta_0 + \beta_1 LNOIL_t + \beta_2 LNMFG_t + \beta_3 LNSVC_t + \beta_4 LNAGR_t + \mu_t \dots\dots\dots (4)$$

Where:

DIV = Diversification index (proxied by RGDP), OIL = oil sector contribution, MFG = manufacturing sector contribution, SVC = service sector contribution and AGR = agricultural sector contribution.

β_0 = Intercept of the model, $\beta_1 - \beta_4$ = Structural parameters of the model to be estimated, μ_t = Stochastic error term, and other variables are as previously defined, t = time variant and LN = Natural logarithm of the variables.

3.3 A-priori Expectation

The a-priori expectation of the model is such that $\beta_1 > 0$, $\beta_2 > 0$, $\beta_3 > 0$, and $\beta_4 > 0$; that is to

say that the oil sector contribution, manufacturing sector contribution, service sector contribution and agricultural sector contribution are all expected to have positive effects on the economic diversification of Nigeria.

3.4 Pre-Estimation Test

3.4.1 Unit Root Test

To fully explore the data generating process, we first examined the time series properties of model variables using the Augmented Dickey-Fuller test.

The ADF test regression equations with constant are:

$$\Delta Y_T = \alpha_0 + \alpha_1 Y_{T-1} + \sum_{j=1}^k a_j \Delta Y_{T-1} + \varepsilon_T \dots \dots \dots (5)$$

where Δ is the first difference operator ε_T is random error term that is iid k = no of lagged differences Y = the variable. The unit root test is then carried out under the null hypothesis $\alpha = 0$ against the alternative hypothesis of $\alpha < 0$. Once a value for the test statistics

$$ADF_T = \frac{\hat{\alpha}}{SE(\alpha)} \dots \dots \dots (6)$$

is computed we shall compare it with the relevant critical value for the Dickey-Fuller Test. If the test statistic is greater (in absolute value) than the critical value at 5% or 1% level of significance, then the null hypothesis of $\alpha = 0$ is rejected and no unit root is present. If the variables are non-

stationary at level form and integrated of the same order, this implies evidence of co-integration in the model.

3.5 Data estimation method

This work set out to present an Autoregressive Distributed Lag (ARDL) model. The ARDL model is stated as:

$$LNDIV_t = \beta_0 + \sum_{i=0}^k \beta_1 LNOIL_{t-1} + \sum_{i=0}^k \beta_2 LNMFG_{t-1} + \sum_{i=0}^k \beta_3 LNSVC_{t-1} + \dots \dots \dots$$

In order to obtain the co-integrating equation, equation (7) is transformed into (8) as follows:

$$\Delta LNDIV_t = \beta_0 + \sum_{i=0}^k \beta_1 \Delta LNOIL_{t-1} + \sum_{i=0}^k \beta_2 \Delta LNMFG_{t-1} + \sum_{i=0}^k \beta_3 \Delta LNSVC_{t-1} + \dots \dots \dots$$

$$\text{Where: } ECT_{t-1} = \Delta Y_t - \alpha_0 + \sum \beta_i \Delta Y_{t-i} + \sum \gamma_j \Delta X_{t-j} + \lambda ECT_{t-1} + \varepsilon_t \dots \dots \dots (9)$$

The ECT represents the deviation from the long-run equilibrium in the previous period. It measures how quickly the dependent variable returns to equilibrium after a change in independent variables. In the ARDL model, the adjustment mechanism incorporates both short-run dynamics and the long-run relationship between variables. The ECT is part of this mechanism. The coefficient of the ECT indicates the speed of adjustment. It should be negative and statistically significant for the model to be valid. The value ranges from -1 to 0, where -1 indicates immediate adjustment (100% correction in one period) and 0 indicates no adjustment.

The Bound test procedure used equations (8) and (9) into (10) as:

$$\Delta Y_t = -\sum_{i=1}^{p-1} \gamma_i Y_{t-i} * \Delta Y_{t-i} + \sum_{i=0}^p \beta_i \Delta X_{t-i} - \rho Y_{t-1} - \alpha - \sum_{i=0}^p \delta X_{t-i} + \mu_t \quad (10)$$

Then we test the existence of level relationship as $\rho = 0$ and $\delta_1 = \delta_2 = \dots = \delta_k = 0$ where Δ = difference operator, α = the short term coefficient, β = the long run coefficients = white noise error term.

3.6 Justification of the Model

The use of ARDL test approach is predicated on its several advantages over other cointegration tests such as Engle-Granger and Johansen's cointegration method. Firstly, the ARDL efficiently determines the cointegrating relation in small sample cases (Ghatak & Siddiki, 2001; Tang, 2003), whereas Johansen's method requires large sample for validity. Secondly, other methods requires that the variables must be integrated of the same order before the cointegration test is carried out, while the ARDL approach can be applied irrespective of whether the regressors are I(1)

and I(0) or mutually cointegrated, in which the dependent variable must be I(1).

3.7 Test of Significance

The significance was tested at 5% level of significance using the coefficients of the independent variables and following the Rule: Reject the Null hypothesis if the t-prob is less than 0.05, otherwise accept the Null hypothesis when t-prob is greater than 0.05, i.e. Reject if t-prob < 0.05, Accept if t-prob > 0.05.

3.8 Test of Hypotheses

The Hypotheses were tested using the probability of f-statistics: Reject the Null hypothesis if the probability of f-statistics is less than the critical value (0.05), otherwise accept the Null hypothesis when critical value (0.05) exceeds probability of f-statistics.

4.0 DATA PRESENTATION, ANALYSIS AND INTERPRETATION

4.1 Data Presentation

4.1.1 Unit Root Test Result

The Augmented Dickey Fuller (ADF) unit root test is summarized in the Table 4.1 below. This test was carried out on each of the variables at 5% critical value.

Table 4.1: Summary of ADF test results at 5% critical value

		ADF Test statistics			
Variable		At Level	1 st Difference	Decision	Order of Integration
LNDIV		-0.641667	-3.930270	Stationary at 1 st difference	I(1)
LNOIL		-3.819780	-	Stationary at level	I(0)
LNMFG		-2.538126	-3.286353	Stationary at 1 st difference	I(1)
LNSVC		-4.042557	-	Stationary at level	I(0)
LNAGR		-3.622488	-	Stationary at level	I(0)
Critical Values	1%	-3.626784	-3.626784		
	5%	-2.945842	-2.945842		
	10%	-2.611531	-2.611531		

Source: Researcher's Computation using *E-Views 13 (2025)*

The unit root test in table 4.1 above reveals that oil sector contribution to economic diversification in Nigeria (LNOIL), services sector contribution to economic diversification in Nigeria (LNSVC) and agricultural contribution to economic diversification in Nigeria (LNAGR) are stationary at level and are said to be integrated of order zero, I(0). Conversely, diversification index (LNDIV) and manufacturing sector contribution to economic

diversification in Nigeria (LNMFG) are stationary at first difference and are said to be integrated of order one I(1). Thus, the autoregressive distributed lag (ARDL) technique becomes appropriate in estimating the relationship among the variables. However, we first confirm the existence of a long-run relationship or co-integrating relationship amongst the variables using the ARDL Bounds test.

4.1.2 ARDL Bounds Co-Integration Test

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A necessary condition for testing for ARDL bounds co-integrating test is that each of the variables be integrated of either of order one or zero or both (Pesaran, Shin and Smith, 2001). Since all the variables are integrated of order

one and zero (mixed order), we proceed to estimate the ARDL bounds test. The decision rule is to reject the null hypothesis if the F-statistics is greater than the upper bound critical values at chosen level of significance.

Table 4.2: ARDL Bounds Cointegration Test Result (@ 5% critical value)

<i>Mode l</i>	<i>F-Statistics</i>	<i>K</i>	<i>Significance level</i>	<i>Critical Bound Value</i>	
				<i>10 (Lower Bound)</i>	<i>11 (Upper Bound)</i>
	15.662981	4	5%	2.947	4.088

Source: Researcher's Computation with *E-views 13 (2025)*

Table 4.2 above summarizes the Bounds Test F-statistics for co-integration. The F-statistic coefficient (15.662981) is greater than the critical values I(0) and I(1) bounds at 5%. This entails that we reject the null hypothesis and conclude that there is a long run relationship between oil sector contribution (LNOIL), services sector contribution (LNSVC), agricultural sector contribution (LNAGR), manufacturing sector contribution (LNMFG)

and economic diversification in Nigeria. Since there is a long run relationship, we therefore estimate the short run and long run ARDL analysis.

4.1.3 Test for Short Run Relationship

Having ascertained that there exists a co-integrating relationship between oil sector contribution, manufacturing sector contribution, services sector contribution and agricultural sector contribution to economic diversification in Nigeria, the short run relationship needs to be ascertained.

Table 4.3: Summary of Parsimonious Short Run Relationship Between Oil Sector Contribution, Manufacturing Sector Contribution, Services Sector Contribution and Agricultural Sector Contribution and Economic Diversification in Nigeria

Conditional Error Correction Regression				
Variable	Coefficient	Std. Error	t-Statistic	Prob.
CointEq(-1)	-0.013594	0.001301	-10.44680	0.0000

Source: Researcher's Computation with E-views 13 (2025)

From 4.3 above; the coefficient of the error correction term (CointEq) is statistically significant and carries the expected negative sign at 5% level of significance, revealing that a short run relationship exists between oil sector contribution, manufacturing sector contribution, services sector contribution and agricultural sector contribution and economic diversification in Nigeria. The speed of adjustment is -0.013594. This implies that the

model corrects its lagged period disequilibrium at a speed of adjustment of 1.36%. Therefore, holding the explanatory variables at a constant state of increase by 1.36%, they will bring the desired change on the dependent variable.

4.1.4 Test for Long Run Relationship

It's imperative to ascertain the long run relationship that exists between oil sector contribution, manufacturing sector contribution, services sector contribution and agricultural sector contribution and economic diversification in Nigeria.

Table 4.4: Summary of Long Run Relationship Between Oil Sector Contribution, Manufacturing Sector Contribution, Services Sector Contribution and Agricultural Sector Contribution and Economic Diversification in Nigeria

Variable *	Coefficient	Std. Error	t-Statistic	Prob.
LNOIL	-0.241499	1.189802	-0.202974	0.8404
LNMANUFACTURING	6.397424	25.39056	0.251961	0.8027
LNSERVICES	3.190921	10.27976	0.310408	0.7583
LNAGRICULTURE	-8.407088	32.12826	-0.261673	0.7953
C	1.701592	26.41394	0.064420	0.9490

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Source: *Eviews 13 Output*

$$\begin{aligned} CE = & \text{LNRGDP}(-1) - (-0.241499 * \text{LNOIL} + 6.397424 \\ & * \text{LNMANUFACTURING} + 3.190921 * \text{LNSERVICES} \\ & 8.407088 \\ & * \text{LNAGRICULTURE} + 1.701592) \end{aligned}$$

The long run coefficient from table 4.4 above shows that the joint impact of all the regressors (LNOIL, LNMANUFACTURING, LNSERVICES and LNAGRICULTURE) on the dependent variable will amount to 1.701592 units. This is on the basis that they are all held at constant. In other words, if all the explanatory variables are held at constant, it will amount to 1.701592 units contribution to economic diversification in Nigeria (proxied by LNRGDP).

Oil sector contribution (LNOIL) has a negative insignificant coefficient of 0.241499. This implies that oil sector contribution has a negative relationship with economic diversification in Nigeria. Hence, as investment in the oil sector increases by 1 unit, economic diversification in Nigeria retracts by 0.241499 units.

Manufacturing sector contribution (LNMANUFACTURING) has a positive insignificant coefficient of 6.397424. This shows that manufacturing sector contribution has a positive relationship with economic diversification in Nigeria. This indicates that a unit increase in the manufacturing sector

increases economic diversification in Nigeria by 6.397424 units.

Services sector contribution (LNSERVICES) has a positive insignificant coefficient of 3.190921, implying that services sector contribution has a positive relationship with economic diversification in Nigeria. This indicates that as services sector increases by 1 unit, economic diversification in Nigeria expands by 3.190921 units.

Agricultural sector contribution (LNAGRICULTURE) has a negative insignificant coefficient of 8.407088. This implies that agricultural sector contribution has a negative relationship with economic diversification in Nigeria. Hence, as investment in the agricultural sector increases by 1 unit, economic diversification in Nigeria decreases by 8.407088 units.

4.2 Post-Estimation Tests

The post-estimation results show other tests that are necessary in order to ascertain the statistical robustness and predictive ability of the model. They comprise the Breusch-Godfrey serial correlation LM test, ARCH Heteroskedasticity test, Fisher's test, Durbin Watson test for autocorrelation, normality test, CUSUM and CUSUMQ tests, RAMSEY RESET test and the Coefficient of determination (R-squared and Adjusted R-squared), These tests are summarized as follows:

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Table 4.5: Post-Estimation Diagnostic Results

S/N	Test	Probability	Decision
		Model 1	
1.	Breusch-Godfrey serial correlation LM test	F-stat = 0.879591 <i>p-value</i> = 0.4257	No serial correlation.
2.	Durbin Watson Statistic	2.003729	No Autocorrelation
3.	Fisher's Test	F-stat = 2152.146 <i>p-value</i> = 0.000000	The explanatory variables are jointly significant on the dependent variable
4.	ARCH Heteroskedasticity Test	F-stat = 1.267487 <i>p-value</i> = 0.3027	No Heteroskedasticity in the model
5.	Normality Test	Skewness = 0.315301 Kurtosis = 3.048515 Jarque Bera = 0.616685 <i>P-value</i> = 0.734664	Data is normally distributed as the high <i>p-value</i> of the Jaque-Bera has affirmed
6.	CUSUM & CUSUMQ Tests	Within the bounds of 5% significance level	Model is stable
7.	RAMSEY RESET Test	F-stat = 1.599636 <i>p-value</i> = 0.2157	Model is free from specification bias
8.	R-squared and Adjusted R-squared	0.997127 (99.71%) 0.996664 (99.67%)	High explanatory coefficient

Source: *Extracted from E-Views 13 output*

The post-estimation results in Table 4.5 above show that the joint relationship coefficient of the model is significant given the *p-value* of 0.000000 which is less than 0.05 critical value. The Durbin-Watson coefficient of 2.003729 is

within the bounds of 2 than to 0. The serial correlation and heteroscedasticity tests show that the model is free from serial correlation and heteroscedasticity. Normality test indicates that the data is normally distributed. The CUSUM and CUSUMQ tests indicate that the

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model is stable and converges within the bounds of 5% significance level, while the Ramsey Reset test indicates that the model is free from specification bias. The adjusted R-squared which is most suitable for gauging the overall fitness of the model has a value of 0.996664 indicating that 99.67% variations on economic diversification in Nigeria are accounted for by the real sectors and related variables for the period 1986-2023.

4.3 Test of Hypotheses

The individual test was carried out to test for the significance of the independent variables on the dependent variable at 5% level using probability of the t-statistic shown in Table 4.4. The rule applied is: If probability is greater than the prescribed level of 5% or 0.05, accept the null hypothesis, otherwise reject the null hypothesis when probability is less than 0.05.

Hypothesis 1

HO₁: Oil sector contribution has no significant impact to economic diversification in Nigeria.

Conclusion

From table 4.4 above, the probability of t-stat of LNOIL is 0.8404, and greater than 0.05 critical values. Thus, we accept the null hypothesis and conclude that oil sector contribution has no significant impact to economic diversification in Nigeria.

Hypothesis 2

HO₂: Manufacturing sector contribution has no significant effect to economic diversification in Nigeria.

Conclusion

From table 4.4 above, the probability of t-stat of LNMANUFACTURING is 0.8027, and greater than 0.05 critical values. Thus, we accept the null hypothesis and conclude that manufacturing sector contribution has no significant effect to economic diversification in Nigeria.

Hypothesis 3

HO₃: Services sector contribution has no significant effect to economic diversification in Nigeria.

Conclusion

From table 4.4 above, the probability of t-stat of LNSERVICES is 0.7583, and greater than 0.05 critical values. Thus, we accept the null hypothesis and conclude that oil sector contribution to economic diversification in Nigeria has no significant effect.

Hypothesis 4

HO₄: Agricultural sector contribution has no significant impact to economic diversification in Nigeria.

Conclusion

From table 4.4 above, the probability of t-stat of LNAGRICULTURE is 0.7953, and greater than 0.05 critical values. Thus, we accept the null hypothesis and conclude that agricultural

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sector contribution to economic diversification in Nigeria has no significant impact.

4.5 Discussion of Findings

The empirical findings of this study, which revealed statistically insignificant contributions from the oil, manufacturing, services, and agricultural sectors to economic diversification in Nigeria, both contrast and contextualize existing literature. While the positive but insignificant relationship found for the manufacturing sector partially aligns with Afrogha & Afrogha (2022), who identified a negative impact, it contradicts the expectation of strong sectoral leadership for diversification. The negative relationship for the oil sector resonates with the theoretical predictions of Dutch Disease but provides a nuanced empirical counterpart to studies like Njoku, Ndifon & Apaingolo (2025), which highlighted a positive link between petroleum revenue and GDP, suggesting that revenue generation does not equate to structural diversification. Similarly, the negative finding for agriculture contrasts with Adams, Obonyilo & Kolawale (2024) and Kamil, Sevin and Festus (2017), who emphasized its positive contributions, but aligns with Utuk et al. (2023), who noted negative impacts from agricultural value added, pointing to underlying inefficiencies. The overall insignificance across all sectors underscores and empirically validates the identified literature gap, highlighting that

isolated sectoral growth has been insufficient and emphasizing the imperative for integrated, synergistic policy frameworks to move beyond the persistent oil-dependent paradigm.

5.0 SUMMARY OF FINDINGS, CONCLUSION AND RECOMMENDATIONS

5.1 Summary of Findings

The study assessed the impact of economic diversification and the oil sector in Nigeria. The Auto-regressive Distributed Lag (ARDL) and Error Correction Model (ECM) diagnostics were utilized in the estimation of data. The following summarizes the findings of the research work:

- Oil sector has a negative but statistically insignificant contribution to economic diversification in Nigeria.
- Manufacturing sector has a positive but statistically insignificant contribution to economic diversification in Nigeria.
- Services sector has a positive but statistically insignificant contribution to economic diversification in Nigeria.
- Agricultural sector has a negative but statistically insignificant contribution to economic diversification in Nigeria.

5.2 Conclusion

The study assessed the impact of economic diversification and the oil sector in Nigeria from 1986 to 2023 (38 years). Secondary data for the study were sourced from the 2024

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publication of the Central Bank of Nigeria Statistical Bulletin. The Auto-regressive Distributed Lag (ARDL) and Error Correction Model (ECM) diagnostics were utilized in the data estimation. Oil sector contribution, manufacturing sector contribution, services sector contribution and agricultural sector contribution were regressed on economic diversification (proxied by RGDP) in Nigeria in the analysis. The findings of the study revealed that oil sector contribution and agricultural sector contribution posited negative but statistically insignificant effect on economic diversification. Alternatively, manufacturing sector contribution and services sector contribution to economic diversification in Nigeria showed positive but statistically insignificant relationship. The study therefore concluded that other sectors of the Nigerian economy (other than the oil sector) have positive and significant impacts on economic diversification in Nigeria

5.3 Recommendations

The following recommendations are suggested based on the findings of this research:

- Despite its insignificant negative effect, Nigeria should continue reducing reliance on

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oil by investing in alternative sectors (renewable energy, tech, and agro-processing).

- Manufacturing competitiveness should be boosted through provision of incentives (tax breaks, subsidies) to stimulate local production and export diversification.

- Given the positive (though insignificant) effect of the services sector contribution, expanding digital economy and financial services could spur diversification.

- The negative (but insignificant) contribution of the agricultural sector suggests inefficiencies. Investments in mechanization, irrigation, and agro-processing could reverse this trend. Additionally, strengthening linkages between agriculture and manufacturing (agro-industries) could improve diversification.

Overall, based on the research findings that all four sectors (oil, manufacturing, services, and agriculture) have statistically insignificant contributions to economic diversification in Nigeria (whether positive or negative), there should be focus on policy interventions, structural reforms, and strategic investments to enhance diversification.

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